

Carbon markets can support invasive trees' control with biomass-based value chains

R. PIRARD^a, A.M. PETERSEN^a, A. GROBLER^b and O.F. TUCHTEN^b

^aStellenbosch University, 15 Victoria Street, Stellenbosch 7605, South Africa

^bPromethium Carbon, 32 Peter Place, Bryanston 2021, South Africa

Email: pirardr@sun.ac.za

HIGHLIGHTS

- There is a case for value chains using biomass from invasive alien trees to benefit from carbon pricing mechanisms.
- Certification standards' conditions for eligibility partially align with value chains practices.
- Carbon incentives could represent up to 20% of the final product value.
- Biochar is a specific case highly sensitive to the price of carbon credits.
- Complementary adaptation-based funding would ensure feasibility and impact.

SUMMARY

Financial and human resources are insufficient to address environmental and socio-economic threats by invasive alien trees; besides, the financial feasibility of value chains using the biomass (hence contributors to trees removal) is disputed. In South Africa, we study the supporting role of carbon pricing mechanisms for value chains using biomass from invasive alien trees: do such value chains meet carbon credit issuance conditions (eligibility), and are carbon-related revenues significant enough to make a difference? We target three value chains and apply certified methodologies to quantify emissions reductions and incentives levels: biochar, lump charcoal for stoves, chips for steam production in industrial boilers. We find that eligibility depends on standards as their approach and criteria differ, yet the trend is supportive. Besides, the fact that invasive alien trees are an environmental liability has encouraged standards to adopt a more flexible approach and issue credits on the sole condition that clearing operations are sustainable and regardless of other considerations in terms of climate change mitigation impact. Carbon incentives vary greatly among projects and hold potential to make a difference with up to 20% of the final product value. This translates into an 8–95% increase in the maximum affordable biomass supply cost to break even and depending on value chains and assumptions (e.g. market value of carbon credits). For biochar specifically, the prospects of very high-value carbon credits due to the alleged contribution as Carbon Dioxide Removals (CDR) would secure profitability even with very low biochar market prices, which is possibly a game changer to support biochar production in a context where willingness to pay by farmers/users remains low. Overall, our study shows that carbon markets could contribute to the management/eradication of invasive alien trees despite debatable mitigation impacts, but that value chains must also rely on solid markets for their end products to break even.

Keywords: invasive alien species, South Africa, biochar, carbon credits, bioenergy

Potentiel mixte de la tarification du carbone pour réduire les invasions d'arbres exotiques: illustration avec trois chaînes de valeur en Afrique du Sud

R. PIRARD, A.M. PETERSEN, A. GROBLER et O.F. TUCHTEN

Les impacts environnementaux et socio-économiques des arbres invasifs exotiques sont significatifs mais les moyens financiers et humains pour y remédier restent insuffisants. Par ailleurs, les filières susceptibles d'utiliser cette biomasse disponible (et donc de contribuer à l'effort contre les invasions) sont peu rentables. Nous étudions, en Afrique du Sud, la possibilité d'utiliser différents systèmes de valorisation du carbone pour soutenir ces filières: sont-elles éligibles auprès des divers standards pour la distribution de crédits carbone et/ou pour exporter vers l'Europe en bénéficiant de la Directive sur les Énergies Renouvelables; et ces revenus potentiels sont-ils substantiels? Nous étudions trois filières et appliquons les méthodologies officielles des standards pour quantifier les réductions d'émissions et les niveaux d'incitation associés: biochar pour application dans les sols, charbon de bois pour la production de chaleur dans des poêles, et copeaux de bois pour la production de vapeur dans des chaudières industrielles. Nos résultats indiquent que l'éligibilité de ces projets dépend des standards dont les approches et critères diffèrent, cependant la tendance est positive. Le caractère nocif avéré des arbres invasifs exotiques a en effet encouragé les standards à adapter leur approche pour faciliter la distribution de crédits carbone à la seule condition que les opérations d'abattage soient durables; mais ceci se fait au détriment d'une analyse spécifique du rôle des filières (en fonction de l'origine de la biomasse) dans l'atténuation du changement climatique. Les revenus associés à la valorisation du carbone (e.g. vente des crédits carbone) diffèrent largement selon les projets mais peuvent être significatifs en allant jusqu'à 20% de la valeur du produit final. Cela se traduit par la possibilité d'augmenter le coût d'approvisionnement maximum de la biomasse

entre 8–95% tout en maintenant la rentabilité des projets, selon les filières et les hypothèses. Dans le cas spécifique du biochar, la possibilité de bénéficier d'une valeur bien plus grande des crédits carbone en raison de leur classification comme instruments de capture et stockage, permet de garantir une rentabilité même pour la fourchette basse des prix du biochar. Ceci pourrait faire la différence dans un marché du biochar peu mature et avec une demande solvable atone. Notre étude montre donc que les marchés du carbone peuvent contribuer à la gestion durable/éradication des arbres invasifs exotiques en dépit d'une contribution à l'atténuation du changement climatique qui reste incertaine, mais que les filières utilisant cette biomasse restent dépendantes des marchés liés à leurs produits finaux.

Potencial mixto del precio del carbono para reducir las invasiones de árboles exóticos: ilustración con tres cadenas de valor en Sudáfrica

R. PIRARD, A.M. PETERSEN, A. GROBLER y O.F. TUCHTEN

Los recursos financieros y humanos son insuficientes para hacer frente a las amenazas medioambientales y socioeconómicas de los árboles exóticos invasores; además, la viabilidad financiera de las cadenas de valor que utilizan la biomasa (contribuyendo así a la eliminación de los árboles) se pone en entredicho. Se ha estudiado en Sudáfrica el papel de apoyo de los mecanismos de fijación de precios del carbono para las cadenas de valor que utilizan la biomasa procedente de árboles exóticos invasores: ¿cumplen dichas cadenas de valor las condiciones de expedición de créditos de carbono (elegibilidad), y son los ingresos relacionados con el carbono lo suficientemente significativos como para marcar una diferencia? El estudio se centró en tres cadenas de valor y se aplicaron metodologías certificadas para cuantificar la reducción de emisiones y los niveles de incentivos: biocarbón, carbón vegetal en trozos para estufas, y astillas para la producción de vapor en calderas industriales. Se descubrió que la elegibilidad depende de cada estándar, ya que tienen enfoques y criterios diferentes, pero la tendencia es favorable. Además, el hecho de que los árboles exóticos invasores constituyan una responsabilidad medioambiental ha animado a los estándares a adoptar un enfoque más flexible y a emitir créditos con la única condición de que las operaciones de desbroce sean sostenibles, independientemente de otras consideraciones en términos de impacto de mitigación del cambio climático. Los incentivos al carbono varían mucho entre proyectos y tienen potencial para marcar una diferencia de hasta un 20% del valor final del producto. Esto se traduce en un aumento del 8–95% en el coste máximo asequible del suministro de biomasa para alcanzar el umbral de rentabilidad, dependiendo de las cadenas de valor y de los supuestos (p. ej. el valor de mercado de los créditos de carbono). En el caso concreto del biocarbón, las perspectivas de créditos de carbono de muy alto valor debido a la supuesta contribución a la eliminación de dióxido de carbono garantizarían la rentabilidad incluso con precios de mercado del biocarbón muy bajos, lo que posiblemente suponga un catalizador para apoyar la producción de biocarbón en un contexto en el que la disposición a pagar de los agricultores/usuarios sigue siendo baja. En general, nuestro estudio muestra que los mercados de carbono podrían contribuir a la gestión y erradicación de árboles exóticos invasores a pesar de los discutibles efectos de mitigación, pero que las cadenas de valor también deben depender de mercados sólidos para sus productos finales para alcanzar el umbral de rentabilidad.

INTRODUCTION

Invasive alien trees (hereafter referred to as invasive trees) in South Africa have been identified as a critical threat to biodiversity, water supplies and productive use of land (Everson *et al.* 2014, Holmes *et al.* 2020, Le Maitre *et al.* 2002 & 2016, Ndhlovu *et al.* 2011, O'Connor *et al.* 2020). In order to address this problem an ambitious governmental programme has been in place for almost three decades – Working for Water (WfW) (van Wilgen and Wannenburg 2016). While it helped the country to slow down the propagation of the main species of invasive trees, which were found over 18 million hectares at various densities (Kotzé *et al.* 2010), it is still far from achieving its objectives mainly due to a lack of funding and efficiency in its operations (van Wilgen *et al.* 2022).

Operations implemented by WfW usually include logging and stacking the trees on the site followed by chemical treatments to prevent regrowth. It remains the exception that the biomass from the invasive trees is subsequently used and processed despite myriad possible end-products (Stafford *et al.* 2018). Among these products, both bioenergy and biochar are promising options: bioenergy can diversify energy sources domestically in a context of energy crisis in South Africa but also for export markets such as Europe under the Renewable

Energy Directive (RED); biochar bolsters agriculture's resilience in response to climate change but South Africa relies on Chinese imports to meet an increasing demand (TOMA-Now 2021, Hugo 2016).

Bioenergy may also play a critical role in the decarbonisation of the economy because the South African energy sector is overly reliant on fossil fuels and all types of renewable energy will be expected to contribute to emissions reductions (Akinbami *et al.* 2021). For the country to achieve its objectives as part of the Paris Agreement, it is required to extend significantly its renewable energy capacity; besides, using biomass from invasive trees would lower the risks associated with the large-scale deployment of negative emission technologies in terms of land use competition with consequences on water availability and food security (Afrane *et al.* 2024). As for biochar, it is being increasingly praised for both its potential (Lefebvre *et al.* 2023) and variety of uses and co-benefits (Schmidt and Wilson 2014) globally but also a source of attention nationally to ensure long-term carbon storage in soils (Konz *et al.* 2015).

The idea of harnessing value-added industries to support efforts to eradicate or at least control invasive trees was reviewed in Pirard (2023) who pointed to their contested financial feasibility. As the eradication of invasive trees in

South Africa is a consensual objective for adaptation to climate change (Holden *et al.* 2021) and is also supported by an assessment at the global level concluding that “*Invasive alien species are a major threat to nature [...] and good quality of life*” (IPBES 2023), it is critical to find the means to support bioenergy and biochar using their biomass. Yet, payments for environmental services, including through subsidy programs are unlikely to be applicable at scale in South Africa (Mbopha *et al.* 2021). In this context, the most mature and developed type of incentives is related to climate change mitigation. It is embodied in carbon pricing mechanisms that include carbon credits markets (compliance and voluntary), carbon offsets and carbon tax liabilities (The World Bank 2022).

However, to our knowledge carbon pricing mechanisms have not been studied as a source of revenues that would make invasive trees-based value chains viable. We aim to fill this gap and question the possibility that such mechanisms could change calculations and spur more investments in bioenergy and biochar value chains and in turn contribute to the eradication of tree invasions. Two conditions must be met to achieve this outcome: (i) a carbon accounting paradigm that would make the processing of biomass collected from land clearing of invaded areas eligible and associated with emissions reductions, and (ii) a carbon pricing that is high enough to make such value chains competitive, e.g. through the sales of carbon credits. The first condition is controversial as cutting down trees results in an outright loss of above-ground carbon stocks, and the second condition is challenged by the relatively low price of carbon credits on voluntary markets (Forest Trends' Ecosystem Marketplace 2023).

Yet not only invasive trees must be cut down for legal and environmental reasons in South Africa but land clearing operations for the last couple of decades reportedly leave trees on site, unused; therefore the attribution of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (associated with land clearing) to processing industries is not straightforward and can be disputed. Furthermore, the results from carbon accounting associated with invasive alien trees removal is not straightforward and several factors such as soil carbon dynamics, increased fire risks and albedo change may change the calculations in terms of carbon loss or gain (Nuñez *et al.* 2021). Besides, carbon prices may increase significantly in the coming years due to more aggressive climate change mitigation policies with a sense of urgency. This is also pushed by the interest of corporations to use claims and credits for their own market purposes (Trouwloon *et al.* 2023).

These various elements make it relevant to ask the following research question: is there a case for carbon pricing mechanisms to support selected value chains based on invasive trees in South Africa? This translates into two main secondary questions: do existing methodologies by the main standards make biomass from invasive trees eligible for carbon pricing mechanisms; and would such mechanisms make a difference for the financial feasibility of selected value chains?

The paper presents our methods, then results regarding eligibility of value chains as well as net carbon gains and

resulting carbon-related revenues for three selected types of projects (biochar, lump charcoal in cookstoves, chips for steam in industrial boilers), and a discussion of critical issues and conclusive messages.

METHODS

Eligibility of value chains for carbon pricing mechanisms

The eligibility of the value chains is assessed for two carbon pricing mechanisms: issuance of carbon credits and the European Renewable Energy Directive (RED). The former refers to credits that can be marketed to a diversity of buyers such as individuals or companies that aim to compensate their own emissions, while the latter refers to a scheme that promotes sources of energy that are deemed carbon neutral and allows their users in Europe to reduce their carbon tax liability. The assessment relies on a combination of desk review of official documents for several carbon certification standards (hereafter standards). We also searched through the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) website database to identify relevant definitions for renewable biomass as an eligibility criterion, and for Project Design Documents and Validation reports to study the application of such definitions and methodologies in past and similar projects.

Selected standards cover a diversity of situations, and/or have relations to the South African context, and/or are leaders in the carbon space. The voluntary carbon markets are addressed by the Verified Carbon Standard (VCS), the CDM (now transitioning), and Puro.earth. Exports under the European RED are addressed with the Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials (RSB) and the Sustainable Biomass Program (SBP). The Carbon Offset mechanism in the South African Carbon Tax system is addressed by VCS and CDM. Note also that interviews took place with representatives of VCS/VERRA, RSB and SBP and served to clarify interpretation issues regarding their methodologies.

Quantification of emissions reductions/removals

The quantification of the emissions reductions and removals in real-life applications is undertaken as per the requirements of approved methodologies for registration as carbon credit projects. The three projects/methodologies considered in our study are:

- Project 1: Biochar
Methodology: Puro.earth's Biochar Methodology, version 2. This methodology quantifies the net CO₂-eq removal achieved over the time horizon of 100 years by the production of biochar, when used in various applications. CO₂-eq removal results from the conversion of biomass to biochar with long-term chemical and biological stability. The quantification of these emissions must follow standard Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methods (ISO14040/44), which includes all GHG converted into CO₂-eq.

- Project 2: Small-scale stoves
Methodology: CDM methodology AMS-I.I (Biogas/biomass thermal applications for households/small users), version 6 (Clean Development Mechanism 2022a). This methodology includes the generation of renewable thermal energy using renewable biomass or biogas, e.g. the use of biomass-based solid fuels to displace more GHG-intensive coal in stoves. In our study, we consider lump charcoal as it avoids hazardous emissions associated with unprocessed biomass.
- Project 3: Industrial boilers
Methodology: CDM methodology AM0036 (Use of biomass in heat generation equipment), version 7 (Clean Development Mechanism 2022b). This methodology includes activities that operate biomass (co)-fired heat generation equipment either with retrofit or replacement of existing equipment or with the installation of new equipment. Typical projects involve switching from fossil fuels to biomass. In our study, we consider wood chips as fuel to substitute coal.

The selected projects are hypothetical but realistic cases, and our calculations reflect those applied to a real project with inputs generated through various methods, including modelling. The processes are represented on Figure 1.

Inputs such as volumes of biomass required per unit of output and GHG emissions are generated with process simulations using Aspen Plus program and applying guidance from the methodologies provided by the standards. These process simulations, in turn, rely on conversion rates in reactor units, temperature and pressure of operating units, and thermodynamic models that are based either on the literature or laboratory measurements at Stellenbosch University (Table 1). Besides, data derived from the simulated mass and energy balance was used to populate a LCA model in SimaPro. The LCA also includes other upstream stages of the value chain (via the Eco-invent database) such as biomass harvesting, handling and transportation to factory gates.

It is assumed that biomass is harvested in the Western Cape province where invasive alien trees are made principally of acacias, pines and eucalyptus species (Petersen *et al.* 2022). These trees are logged and chipped on the roadside then the biomass is delivered at the processing site (biomass supply will refer to chips in the remainder of the manuscript). We assume an average distance of 30 km for biomass delivery to be enough for the commercial facilities considered in our study to operate at full capacity. The chipper has a diesel consumption rate of 0.5 L diesel per m³ of chips (Spinelli and Magagnotti 2014). Transport by truck consumes 59 litres of fuel per 100 km with a payload of 31.1 tons (Konz *et al.* 2015).

Production costs

The economic side of the analysis requires various capital and operating costs, and the basis of these estimations are the mass and energy balances that are generated in Aspen Plus to reflect the physical processes involved. The mass and energy

balances are then linked to specific costs, which are obtained from personal communications with industrial actors and secondary data from literature (see a previous database similarly created by the authors – Petersen *et al.* 2020). Fixed operating costs are set as 3.7% of the total capital investment, which is a commonly assumed value in pre-feasibility studies (*ibid*). Variable operating costs are estimated using the mass and energy flows and market prices. Thus, energy inputs such as diesel are priced at 1.5 US\$/l and 83 US\$/MWh, respectively. In order to calculate the gate-to-gate production costs, i.e. within the gates of the factory (as shown in Figure 2), the financial flows over the payback period of 25 years are subjected to a discount rate of 12%, an accelerated depreciation over 5 years, and a taxation rate of 28% (*ibid*).

The gate-to-gate production costs are then subtracted from the market prices and scaled with the yield to come up with the maximum affordable biomass supply costs (hereafter maximum supply costs) compatible with the financial feasibility once the 12% discount rate is applied for each project. These maximum supply costs are calculated with and without revenues from the sale of carbon credits and are a meaningful way to analyse the impact of such additional revenues.

Estimation of carbon credit revenues and costs

The revenues generated by the three types of projects are related to both the emissions reductions/removals and the carbon credit prices. Internationally, the carbon standards with the highest market shares include the CDM which is transitioning to the Article 6.4 Mechanism, the VCS, and the Gold Standard for Global Goals. Pricing information is not publicly disclosed, and estimations are derived from open market sources reporting on price estimates and pricing trends.

The South African Carbon Tax system allows carbon taxpayers to reduce their carbon tax liability through various allowances, including a carbon offset allowance, as outlined in the Carbon Tax Act No.15 of 2019. Under the Carbon Offset Regulations, carbon credits generated through the CDM, VCS, and Gold Standard can be used, as well as approved domestic standards. Pricing details within this market are not publicly available however, it is assumed that taxpayers would acquire carbon credits at a value lower than the carbon tax rate (see below).

In addition to the voluntary and Carbon Tax markets in South Africa, an international carbon market is developing under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement. It recognises that some countries may opt for voluntary cooperation in the implementation of their Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC) and establishes the framework for the market mechanisms. Of relevance to this work is Article 6.2, which introduces another carbon credit unit known as Internationally Transferred Mitigation Outcomes (ITMOs). ITMOs include both emissions reductions and removals, indicating the presence of an additional avenue within Article 6.2 for certifying emissions reduction projects and potentially trading carbon credits. Pricing trends are not available for this developing market and the operational requirements for implementing Article 6.2 have not yet been put into effect in South Africa.

FIGURE 1 Production flowcharts for biochar, lump charcoal and steam using biomass from invasive trees

Note: Part A is for Project 1, Part B is for Project 2, Part C is for Project 3

We do not provide any revenue or cost estimations for the case of biomass-based products such as pellets exported to Europe under the Renewable Energy Directive (RED). The business rationale is to get a premium due to the qualification of such products as carbon-neutral, which enables buyers in Europe to escape the carbon tax. Therefore, the only financial condition to meet for producers in South Africa is that their production costs (including transport and certification by so-called recognised schemes in Europe) would not exceed the market price in Europe. In our study, we limit ourselves to

the analysis of their eligibility for two major standards (“recognised schemes” in the RED terminology) with operations in South Africa.

Justification of low and high carbon pricing scenarios

In our sensitivity analysis, the low carbon pricing scenario uses the average VCS trading price of US\$ 9 in 2023 (Forest Trends’ Ecosystem Marketplace 2023). This trading price is a proxy for the lower prices in the voluntary carbon market considering that VCS dominates voluntary carbon markets.

TABLE 1 *Methods and inputs for the quantification of emissions reductions*

Inputs	Project	Description
Scope (according to methodology provided by standards)	1	Emissions associated with the various activities in the value chain: supplies of biomass including harvesting and transport, conversion to biochar and application in the soil
	2	Emissions associated with the various activities in the value chain: supplies of biomass including harvesting and transport, conversion to lump charcoal and use in cookstoves
	3	Emissions associated with the various activities in the value chain: supplies of biomass including harvesting and transport, and the electricity usage at the steam plant
Supplies of biomass as feedstock in the production processes	1, 2, 3	The description of the assumed logistics is a secondary data source, as it stems primarily from research conducted on industrial practice and average energy inputs for electricity. SimaPro calculates the emissions associated with transport and chipping, based on average values from industry
Process descriptions	1	The description is from a primary data source conveyed by an industry representative. Conditions and performance of the units were derived experimentally at Stellenbosch University
	2	The description is from a primary data source conveyed by an industry representative. Conditions and performance of the units were derived experimentally at Stellenbosch University
	3	The description is from a secondary data source, based on descriptions found in literature on industrial steam production
Assumptions / default values	1, 2, 3	Emissions from transport are the same per ton of lump charcoal, chips or biochar. Emissions from harvesting are primarily from biomass chipping due to negligible emissions associated with tree felling
Constraints		Mass and energy flows are all simulated in Aspen Plus. Emission factors applied to mass and energy flows are all from the LCA software database

FIGURE 2 *Gate-to-gate production costs for each of the three projects under consideration (excluding feedstock supplies costs)*

This pricing is based on average prices and is thus conservative. Indeed, prices could vary significantly for waste biomass projects, where these have demonstrable co-benefits such as reduction of waste, circular economy and biodiversity impacts such as in our cases.

The high carbon pricing scenario uses the legislated South African carbon tax rates. The analysis for revenues generated

within this system assumes (based on the authors' experience) that carbon credits would be valued at 80% of the legislated Carbon Tax rate for 2030 of R462/t CO₂-eq, hence approximately US\$ 20/t CO₂-eq. This market presents lower uncertainty and pricing variability compared to other markets, given that the Carbon Tax Rate has been legislatively defined up to 2030 (Tax Law Amendment Act of 2023).

RESULTS

Is biomass from invasive trees eligible for carbon credits?

Results are recapitulated in Table 2 and the situations leading to eligibility of value chains are represented in Figure 3. In the following sub-sections, we elaborate on each avenue for the issuance of carbon credits.

Verified Carbon Standard (VCS)

The VCS is the dominant standard for voluntary carbon markets and related carbon credits are eligible as South African carbon offsets.

The VCS released a methodology for biochar, namely “VM0044- Biochar utilization in soil and non-soil applications”

(Biochar Works *et al.* 2022). Its rationale is to make use of biomass that (i) was not grown for the purpose of biochar production, and (ii) is not imported and would have been left to decay or combusted for non-energy purposes. It applies broadly speaking to residues usually from forestry and agricultural or food processing sectors.

The terminology adopted in the methodology is “waste biomass”, which refers to biomass that is available after a first processing stage (e.g. trees after logging, sawdust after milling, vegetable residues after harvesting, animal manure from animal husbandry), has no economic use and is expected to result in emissions from natural decay or combustion processes. Worth noting invasive species are considered explicitly but only for the case of aquaculture, e.g. water Hyacinth would be eligible as feedstock whenever they were not introduced.

TABLE 2 *Conditions of eligibility for use of biomass from invasive trees in South Africa according to carbon pricing mechanisms*

Mechanism	Relevant methodologies	Approach / concept used	Conditions of eligibility for biomass from invasive trees (source of feedstock)
VCS	Biochar (VM0044)	Waste biomass	Trees are cut down for land management reasons and not for biomass supply purposes
Puro.earth	Biochar methodology	Invasive species	Use of invasive species (recognised as such by competent authority) Carbonization is not mandated or legally required by relevant authorities Procedures in place to differentiate the invasive species from other local species
CDM	AMS-I.D on “Grid connected renewable electricity generation” AMS-I.I on “Biogas/biomass thermal applications for households/small users” AMS-III.AS on “Switch from fossil fuel to biomass in existing manufacturing facilities for non-energy applications” AM0036 on “Use of biomass in heat generation equipment”	Renewable biomass	Harvesting operations are sustainable Biomass is woody biomass produced sustainably from croplands and/or grasslands that remain so or are reverted to forest
Carbon Offset Mechanism in South Africa (to reduce carbon tax liability)	VCS, CDM and Gold Standard are accepted	Waste biomass or renewable biomass depending on standard used	Same as stated above for waste or renewable biomass
Renewable Energy Directive	RSB SBP	Status as alien invasive plants Prevention of environmental degradations	Harvesting operations are sustainable Legal requirements for land clearing and status as alien invasive plants are sufficient in terms of feedstock origin Harvesting operations are sustainable There is no land conversion involved (forests, wetlands, peatlands, highly biodiverse grasslands) compared to land status in 2008 Carbon stocks must be stable or increased at landscape level

Note: “Harvesting operations are sustainable” includes harvesting techniques, soil and ecosystem damage; for the Renewable Energy Directive we only included two schemes with most relevant activities in South Africa (but other schemes exist); VCS = Verified Carbon Standard; CDM = Clean Development Mechanism; RSB = Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials; SBP = Sustainable Biomass Program

FIGURE 3 Situations leading to eligibility of using invasive trees biomass for the issuance of carbon credits according to standards' methodologies

Source: Own results

To assess the eligibility of biomass from invasive trees, two cases must be distinguished: (i) biomass comes from sites where existing land clearing programmes have been operating and the resource is collected after these business-as-usual logging operations (alien clearing is the driving factor), or (ii) sites are cleared by operators to supply processing facilities (biomass supply is the driving factor). The former case qualifies as waste biomass (land clearing and biomass supplies are two independent operations), but the latter case is not straightforward. Although the resource is not grown for the purpose of biochar production, land clearing may not have happened in the absence of such production thus disqualifying the concept of waste biomass. This is a grey area (Figure 3) addressed in the Discussion section.

Puro.earth

Puro.earth specialises in carbon removals and is not recognised under the South African carbon tax system, meaning that credits can only be used in the voluntary carbon market. It has developed a biochar methodology, which is qualified as a case of CO₂ removal achieved over a period of 100 years when used in applications "placed in the environment" to guarantee the permanence of storage. It has the unique characteristic among standards to address explicitly the use of invasive species that "are causing environmental harm". Eligibility is then based on compliance with three conditions:

there is recognition of invasive species by national authorities, there is no legal requirement to carbonise cleared waste, and the biomass supplier has procedures in place to avoid unintended clearing of native vegetation. All these conditions are automatically met in South Africa apart from the latter one, which may be easily met by the carbon project developers to receive carbon credits (Figure 3).

Clean Development Mechanism (CDM)

The CDM is one of the best-known standards and is facing a transition period; it is recognised under the South African carbon tax system. Several methodologies under the CDM are highly relevant to our study as they cover a wide spectrum of cases with either electricity supplied to the grid, or heat and power in decentralised units such as chicken farms.

Eligibility of biomass rests on the concept of "renewable biomass", which originates in the document EB 23 Annex 18 of the UNFCCC. This document indicates that one of five conditions must apply, of which three apply explicitly to woody biomass:

- Biomass is produced sustainably from a forest area that remains so;
- Biomass residues whose collection does not involve a decrease of carbon pools (e.g. dead wood or litter) on the land of origin – dead wood collection from a forest is not considered as renewable;

- Biomass is woody biomass produced sustainably from croplands and/or grasslands that remain so or are reverted to forest.

The first two conditions tend to make CDM more conservative than the VCS concept of “waste biomass”; but the third condition could easily be met with biomass from invasive trees if we interpret it in terms of land use rather than land cover. Indeed, it would apply to land clearing for the purpose of returning an area or ecosystem to its original state before invasions (e.g. putting land back to farming or grazing). Furthermore, and this is a critical point, the causality is not mentioned so that clearing can be done for the explicit purpose of supplying processing facilities (Figure 3).

This line of reasoning is strengthened by the only existing Project Design Document (CDM Executive Board 2012) with a case of biomass from invasive trees; moreover, this project takes place in South Africa and corresponds to the methodology AMS-I.D (Table 2). It stresses the legal obligations to eradicate invasive species according to the Biodiversity Convention but also national laws with the Conservation of Agricultural Resources Act (Act 43 of 1984). The validation report explains that land clearing will be followed by the reintroduction of crops or indigenous vegetation, which in turn leads to meeting the condition of remaining cropland/grassland. As a conclusion: “*the validation team confirms that the identified IAPs [Invasive Alien Plants] are woody renewable biomass*”. Furthermore, the validation team goes on by explaining that “*alien vegetation (woody) biomass will be harvested from farmland (i.e. grassland or cropland) that has been overrun by IAPs*” (Bunge Emissions Holdings SARL 2012).

A reference is also made to a consultation paper by the National Energy Regulator of South Africa (NERSA 2011) on a Review of Renewable Energy Feed-in-tariff. In this document the definition of renewable biomass is made along the lines of UNFCCC document EB 23 Annex 18 but adds one specific case: “*The biomass is from a non-native and invasive plant that has not been grown specifically for the purposes of biomass fuel production*”. Its formal adoption would pave the way to the allocation of public support in the form of feed-in-tariffs but would not necessarily strengthen the case for the eligibility to VCS and/or CDM methodologies.

Is biomass from invasive trees eligible for exports to Europe via the Renewable Energy Directive (RED)?

Due to an unsupportive policy and fiscal environment, some bioenergy industries may opt for the export markets and particularly the European Union where the RED offers incentives to pellets for energy generation based on their assumed low carbon emissions (e.g. the operating company Coega Biomass Center). Eligibility for RED requires certification by a recognised scheme, of which SBP has been applied in South Africa and RSB is working towards an application to invasive trees with pilot activities and dedicated rules. Results are presented in Table 2 and elaborated for each standard below.

Sustainable Biomass Program (SBP)

Eligibility depends on several Principles (all of them must be verified), of which two are relevant to our case. According to Principle 2, the feedstock must not be sourced from “*land that had one of the following statuses in January 2008 and no longer has that status due to land conversion: a. Forests b. Wetlands c. Peatlands d. Highly biodiverse grasslands*” (<https://sbp-cert.org/documents/normative-documents/version-2/standards-v2/> - SBP 2023). The only case where land clearing of invaded lands would not be eligible is thus when densely invaded areas are classified as forests due to sufficiently high densities and duration of invasions. But this remains open to interpretation.

According to Principle 3, feedstock must be sourced from supply bases where the forest carbon stock is stable or increasing in the long term. This is hardly applicable to land clearing to restore ecosystems except if land use prevails over land cover. Indeed, one could argue that invaded croplands or grasslands have corresponding carbon stocks so that removing trees (change of land cover but not land use) is not associated with the release of above-ground carbon. Here again, eligibility remains open to interpretation.

More important, the scheme is currently changing its modus operandi. The pellet manufacturer and exporter Coega Biomass Center was certified during a first phase when FSC (Forest Stewardship Council) certification of harvesting and post-removal operations was deemed a sufficient condition. Yet FSC certification only guarantees the sustainability of forestry practices, which does not include the reconstitution of stocks: it is thus irrelevant for climate change mitigation. SBP is now changing the approach and requires that all conditions included in their Standard 1 be applied. At the time of writing, such changes and their implications were not clear yet. But it is worth noting that with sustainability at the core of SBP principles, operations conducted by WfW could as well be ineligible depending on their quality.

Roundtable on Sustainable Biomaterials (RSB)

The other scheme RSB is highly relevant to our case due to the special consideration of invasive trees in an amendment released in 2021 on woody biomass with a section dedicated to alien invasive plants (AIP) with related biomass defined as “*material from [AIP] that is generated as a waste by an operation cleaning an invaded area*”. If the eradication of invasive trees complies with RSB Principles & Criteria (e.g. is legal, respects human and labour rights), then it is eligible.

At the time of writing this amendment dedicated to woody biomass could not yet be used for certification and eligibility to RED. But if and when it does, RSB rules will become very clear and will provide carbon neutrality (carbon accounting starts from the collection at the point of origin after logging) to biomass from invaded areas whatever the reasons for land clearing. The emphasis will rather be on the need for land restoration.

Such a standard might thus offer a golden opportunity for any pellet (or equivalent) producer from South Africa to benefit from RED incentives. This country is also a primary target, it will indeed host the RSB pilot activities about to be

implemented in 2024 to test, refine and clarify the rules based on lessons learned from the field.

Carbon flows and simulations of carbon revenues

We provide below the estimations for revenues from carbon credits; as justified in the Methods section we do not provide estimations for the case of exports under the RED.

Emissions reductions and removals

For project 1 the potential sequestration per ton of biochar based on the Puro.earth (2022) methodology that considers permanence over 100+ years is about 2.6 ton CO₂-eq (Table 3). It represents 81% of the theoretical amount of CO₂ that can be emitted from the carbon contained in the biochar during complete combustion. When considering the emissions involved in the production process (harvesting, pyrolysis, etc.) as per the methodology, the net value is 2.418 ton CO₂-eq per ton.

For project 2, one GJ of energy for households and small users with cookstoves requires 43 kg of coal; when coal is substituted by lump charcoal then the associated GHG emissions are reduced by 95%. This is equivalent to a GHG reduction of 2.24 kg CO₂-eq per kg of lump charcoal. The GHG emissions embodied in the lump charcoal are principally due to the emissions in the pyrolysis process, where 2.55 dry tons of biomass are converted into 1 ton of lump charcoal.

For project 3, respectively 118 kg of coal and 200 kg of biomass are required to produce 1 ton of steam. GHG emissions are reduced by 88% when using biomass, and the bulk of the remaining emissions is due to biomass supply operations.

Overall, these results indicate that the contribution in terms of emissions reductions varies for the three projects when calculated per ton of biomass processed. This is due to the efficiency of the processing technologies that differ depending on whether the product would be biochar or heat generation either from stoves or industrial boilers. Project 3 leads to a significant increase in emissions reductions (about 1.3 t CO₂-eq/t biomass) compared to the other two projects (0.8–0.9 t CO₂-eq/t biomass). The main implication is that the level of incentives is expected to be significantly higher for project 3 when calculated per ton of biomass processed as presented in the next sub-section.

Revenues from the sale of carbon credits

The significance of revenues from the sale of carbon credits for value chains (Table 4) depends eventually on the value of the end-product, which is highly variable in our three projects. For instance, while the project 1 generates a much higher amount of carbon credits per ton of output than project 3 (respectively US\$ 36/ton of biochar and US\$ 4/ton of steam considering a unit price of US\$ 15/ton CO₂-eq for carbon credits), these carbon-related revenues amount respectively to 4% and 20% of the value of the commercial product.

TABLE 3 *Quantification of emissions reductions: key physical inputs and outputs*

Project 1: Biochar		
Methodology: Puro-Earth Methodology for Biochar, version 2 (Puro.earth 2022)		
Greenhouse Gases permanently embodied in 1 ton of biochar	2.585	ton CO ₂ -eq
GHG emissions accounted to produce one ton biochar	0.168	ton CO ₂ -eq
Net Greenhouse Gases sequestered per ton biochar	2.418	ton CO ₂ -eq
Biomass required per ton biochar produced	2.931	ton
Project 2: Small-scale cookstoves		
Methodology: CDM's AMS-I.I "Biogas/biomass thermal applications for households/small users", version 6 (Clean Development Mechanism 2022a)		
Coal required per GJ energy	43	kg
Total GHG emissions embodied per GJ energy (coal)	102	kg CO ₂ -eq
Total GHG emissions embodied per GJ energy (lump charcoal)	4.6	kg CO ₂ -eq
Lump charcoal required per GJ energy	38	kg
Net GHG reduction per kg of lump charcoal	2.24	kg CO ₂ -eq
Biomass required to produce 1 ton lump charcoal	2.55	ton
Project 3: Industrial boilers (10 ton of steam generation capacity)		
Methodology: CDM's AM0036 "Use of biomass in heat generation equipment", version 7 (Clean Development Mechanism 2022b)		
Coal required for 10 ton of steam production	1.2	ton
Embodied GHG emissions (per ton of steam generated from coal)	330	kg CO ₂ -eq
Biomass required for 10 ton of steam production	2	ton
Embodied GHG emissions (per ton steam generated from biomass)	39	kg CO ₂ -eq
Net GHG reduction for one ton of steam with fuel substitution	261	kg CO ₂ -eq

Note: With respect to biomass, all measurements refer to dry tons or dry kg

TABLE 4 Quantification of carbon-related revenues: key economic inputs and outputs

Project	Unit	1	2	3
Product		Biochar	Lump charcoal for small-scale stoves	Steam from industrial boilers
Product Value/Price	US\$/ton	1 000	450	20
Maximum affordable supply cost per unit of biomass (without carbon revenues)	US\$/ton	145	82	23
Value of Carbon Credit used as a base case (US\$/ton CO ₂ -eq)	US\$/ton	15	15	15
Revenues from sales of carbon credits per ton of final product	US\$/ton	36	34	4
Revenues from sales of carbon credits compared to final product value	%	4%	7%	20%
Increase in the maximum affordable supply cost per unit of biomass when including carbon revenues	US\$/ton	12	13	22
GHG reduction per ton of biomass processed	Kg CO _{2eq} /ton	825	879	1 464

Note: With respect to biomass, all measurements refer to dry tons or kg

Another meaningful way to look at the results is to translate revenues from carbon credits into an increase in the maximum supply cost for projects to be financially feasible. In other words, carbon revenues provide investors with access to more invaded areas for biomass collection (e.g. over longer distances). This is also important because the value chains under consideration might also have to compete with other sources of feedstock such as wood from dedicated tree plantations, potentially more cost-effective but not benefitting from the carbon-related incentives.

Table 4 shows that maximum affordable supply costs in the absence of carbon credit revenues vary greatly between the three projects (US\$ 23 – US\$ 145 per ton). With carbon credits set at US\$ 15/ton CO₂-eq such maximum values can increase by US\$ 12 – US\$ 22 per ton, which we consider significant at varying degrees depending on projects: increases are respectively 8%, 16% and 95% respectively for biochar, small-scale stoves and industrial boilers. With a more optimistic assumption of US\$ 20/ton CO₂-eq for carbon credits then the increase would be more than double in the case of steam (Project 3).

The differences between projects are largely due to the potential of GHG reduction per ton of biomass processed (Table 3). For instance, it is greatest for project 3 because there is a direct substitution of a fossil fuel with little pre-processing (wood chips). On the contrary, the pyrolysis process for project 1 converts 72% of the initial biomass into volatiles compounds (e.g. hydrogen), which are eventually combusted for energy purposes. Since these gases are not completely oxidised during their combustion for pyrolysis pre-processing, they become a source of GHG generation within the value chain. For project 2 there is also a loss of mass due to pyrolysis pre-processing (yet lower than for project 1). Overall, the more biomass input per ton output and the lower the impact of emissions reductions on the increase

in the maximum biomass supply cost because carbon revenues are distributed across more tons of biomass.

Another point merits consideration with respect to the diversity of methodologies. As the amount of carbon credits is based on the net emissions reductions, it follows that methodologies which assume emissions to be zero for certain stages of the value chain would be more impactful. This is the case for the VCS methodology for biochar (an alternative to Puro.earth) that puts aside the emissions from the pyrolysis process resulting in different quantities of emissions reductions, potentially impacting the project's carbon revenue in a positive way.

Our analysis goes one step further by considering low and high carbon pricing scenarios due to large uncertainties in the evolution of carbon markets (see Methods); the sensitivity analysis is presented in Figure 4. For instance, project 3 would enjoy carbon revenues of US\$ 13 and US\$ 29 per ton of biomass respectively for a carbon credit value of US\$ 9 and US\$ 20. Taking stock of actual reported average supply costs from our interactions with field operators, which we set at US\$ 77.5/ton in the form of chips, carbon revenues would represent the equivalent of respectively 17% or 38% of the average supply costs for project 3.

The case of biochar merits further examination for two reasons. While carbon credits are mostly a commodity, there are also differences in value due to the nature of the activities and the co-benefits (e.g. biodiversity and social impacts). In the case of biochar credits may be sold at much higher prices than average and up to US\$ 100 and more (e.g. <https://puro.earth>). This is because biochar projects are often considered as Carbon Dioxide Removals (Shukla *et al.* 2022), even if this is contested and might change in the future with lower values for related carbon credits (Pirard 2025), and as such of interest to buyers who want to offset their residual emissions (Trouwloon *et al.* 2023). On the other hand, the market price of biochar is also uncertain and highly dependent on the quality of the product.

FIGURE 4 Impacts of the price of carbon credits on maximum biomass supply costs across projects

Figure 5 shows the impact of high value credits. Considering the range of biomass supply costs observed in the field operations (grey area), a minimum biochar price of US\$ 650–700/ton would be required to ensure feasibility for US\$ 25/t CO₂-eq credits. With high-value credits, this minimum biochar price drops at less than US\$ 500/ton.

These variations are critical to consider due to the lack of maturity of the biochar markets and the uncertain access to revenues from high-value carbon credits once more biochar projects will be implemented worldwide and the balance between supply and demand for these specific carbon credits will lead to new equilibrium.

DISCUSSION

In the following sub-sections we discuss our results and provide additional perspectives about the alignment between the issuance of carbon credits and the actual mitigation impacts, which is not guaranteed if only because the application of standards to a given project leads to different outcomes depending on standards. We do not discuss the relevance of promoting value chains to contribute to the management/eradication of invasive alien trees, which is a complex question fully addressed in Pirard (2023).

FIGURE 5 Relationship between market price of carbon credits, maximum biomass supply costs and biochar market price

Ambiguous rules with debatable interpretations for invasive trees

Our findings in terms of project eligibility (Figure 3 and Table 2) show that contrasted approaches co-exist even though they will eventually condition the issuance of carbon credits for use on the same markets with the same price. There is little justification for such differences, especially because any carbon credit should represent the same impact on global warming, and one may expect harmonisation at a later stage. In other words, a given project may (or may not) lead to the issuance of carbon credits depending on the certification standard that is applied; yet the mitigation impact of the project remains the same and carbon credits would be used to compensate emissions elsewhere.

We can also state that these conditions and rules are vague enough to be subject to interpretation as reflected in the following two examples for waste biomass and renewable biomass concepts. The former seems to require some evidence that the biomass was available on site after logging operations would have taken place for unrelated reasons (e.g. ecosystem restoration or fire management) but this criterion may be abused in a context where land clearing is mandatory. Indeed, one could argue that land clearing mainly serves the purpose of abiding by the law in the case of invasive alien trees listed in the Biodiversity Act, the Conservation of Agricultural Resources Act or other relevant regulations. This is all the more contentious that land clearing is not always done by the dedicated WfW programme and myriad companies have been established to either coordinate with landowners to supply specific markets (e.g. pellets and charcoal) and/or get sub-contracted by WfW to clear lands targeted by the government. Furthermore, experience indicates that public end-users of the biomass may use their law enforcement powers to force landowners to cooperate and clear their land when they plan to invest in their own processing capacities (case of Knysna Municipality – interviews). There is thus an increasingly blurred line between land clearing for environmental or biomass supply purposes.

The other concept of renewable biomass (CDM) is ambiguous in its approach to land classification. Grasslands and croplands could be land uses (e.g. the land is dedicated to farming but temporarily not productive) or land cover (e.g. there is actual crop production on the farm), which generates uncertainties for the eligibility of invaded areas. One could assume that scarcely invaded grasslands or croplands would easily retain this classification (both as land use and land cover) and would thus open the door to a CDM project that clears trees for further processing. But the most promising and economically viable cases for supply chains are invaded areas with a high density of trees; only the land use approach would then guarantee the eligibility of using biomass from invasive trees because land cover would rather be associated with forest/woodland (hence ineligible). The only existing project document that corresponds to our case is under the methodology AMS-1.D and seems supportive of the land use interpretation (CDM Executive Board 2012). Yet it is vague

(but validated) and builds on two arguments, namely the legal requirement to clear land and the reversion of the land to either cropland or the previous ecosystem.

Business-as-usual condition: law vs enforcement and coordination with land clearing programs

The waste biomass criterion (VCS mostly) puts business-as-usual scenarios at its core (implicitly), which in turn speaks to two intertwined concepts: what would happen without the industry providing a market for the biomass, and should the responsibility for producing the biomass be attributed to the industry? It is tempting to oppose two clear-cut situations where either the WfW programme or other NGO-supported restoration initiatives clear the land (eligible as waste biomass), or the industry sends harvesting teams to invaded sites to collect the biomass (not eligible as waste biomass). In reality a continuum of situations exist; their interpretation is perilous.

If one follows the letter of the South African law, then all invaded areas will be cleared at one point in time and all resulting biomass is waste biomass. Yet law enforcement is weak and land clearing costs are relatively high so that there is little incentive for landowners to clear. Besides, WfW for all its political support and considerable spending, could only operate on a fraction of invaded lands. Note that the situation can be made more complicated by the emergence of water users associations and irrigation boards that coordinate land clearing operations on behalf of landowners for the purpose of improving water availability, with or without support by the government or biomass markets.

Besides, one can envision a coordination between industries and WfW to make sure that land clearing (subsidised by the government) takes place in sites within economic distance to the processing facilities. This means that the business-as-usual scenario is one where land clearing would have taken place elsewhere while the site selection can be attributed to the industry; this is already happening as landowners can make requests to WfW, possibly coordinating with the industry. Yet such a situation may not lead to rejecting the qualification of waste biomass; rather than leaving or burning biomass, it is processed and creates a win-win situation. Furthermore, it would ensure that the two complementary objectives – invasive trees control and support to value chains – are pursued at the same time. The counterargument that land clearing would then be done in places of low environmental importance and high business interest (e.g. close to road infrastructures and markets) is fragile because the current situation shows that site prioritisation is weak with WfW (van Wilgen *et al.* 2022, Forsyth *et al.* 2012).

Articulating mitigation and adaptation to secure a win-win situation

The control of invasive trees and processing of the biomass include elements of both adaptation and mitigation of climate change: clearing invasive trees renders ecosystems more

resilient and provides environmental services that will be increasingly useful to cope with climate change (e.g. changing rainfall regimes and reduced water availability – e.g. Holden et al. 2021); coal-based energy substitution and biochar production are expected to lead to reduced emissions and carbon storage in the soil. What is up for discussion is how both components interact and how such interaction leads to conclude on the net carbon gains or losses and thus the relevance of using carbon markets to support value chains.

The most logical sequence of action is that adaptation justifies invasive trees control in the first place, which creates a situation whereby biomass processing serves the complementary mitigation objective (Figure 6). This is what implicitly underpins the concept of waste biomass because the mitigation potential is only validated if the biomass is either already available and unused; this might be less true with the concept of renewable biomass where land use is to be reverted to its undisturbed/uninvaded condition because carbon gains or losses are uncertain when all carbon pools are considered (e.g. Nuñez et al. 2021). Funding at scale for adaptation in South Africa would support more land clearing and in turn more biomass available for mitigation via energy substitution or carbon storage in the soil. Furthermore, alien clearing and the supply of biomass could be an alternative to natural carbon release through fires – which are expected to become more frequent with climate change – so that factoring in such

emissions in the business-as-usual scenario (no action) could also be justified; it would strengthen the case for a mitigation benefit and associated carbon revenues as incentives for value chain development.

Yet the current situation is rather one where the private sector explores options to access biomass, which might thus be seen as an increasingly scarce and valuable resource when supply and demand are compared. When this tension on the market is combined with expected gains in access costs (e.g. better logistics and information) and a rush towards alternative energy sources in the midst of a severe national energy crisis, it becomes sensible to assume that land clearing operations are increasingly determined by the demand side. In this context, the case for net carbon gains is undermined because the concept of waste biomass, at least, tends to lose its relevance; adaptation benefits remain but are not the driver of land clearing.

Transaction costs

The significance of carbon revenues must reflect hidden or transaction costs involved in the development of a carbon project (Table 5). The paths leading to certification for either the issuance of carbon credits, offsets to reduce carbon tax liabilities domestically, or eligibility under the RED to access European markets, are complex and we focus on the case of carbon credits for voluntary markets.

FIGURE 6 Articulation between adaptation-based funding and mitigation-based funding to maximise positive impacts and secure eligibility of biomass value chains for carbon pricing mechanisms

TABLE 5 Costs and fees associated with the issuance of carbon credits: a summary

Fees*	Unit	Average across the Carbon Standards
Once off fees, inclusive of account fees and validation fees (Registration fees)	US\$	22 800
Fees incurred when the project issues carbon credits, inclusive of verification audit fees (periodic fees)	US\$	20 000
Issuance fees (periodic fees)	US\$/tCO ₂ -eq	0.25
Annual registry fees paid to the carbon standard (Annual fees)	US\$	750
Monitoring fees** (Annual fees)	US\$	40 000

* The pricing below does not include the technical development costs as charged by a consultancy.

** Monitoring fees vary based on the type of project, the methodology and the technology available. The monitoring fees have been averaged based on project experience.

The various costs indicated correspond to a standard project cycle under the carbon standards (Figure 7). Once a project developer has identified a methodology under a relevant standard and the project meets the minimum requirements of that methodology, the project can apply for registration. Under the VCS and the Gold Standard, this step is referred to as project validation, whereas under Puro.earth it is simply referred to as project registration.

Thereafter, projects are typically required to list for a minimum of 30 days on the standard's website where the public can comment on the documents uploaded by the project (pipeline listing). Projects are often required to undergo a validation audit, which is conducted by third-party independent auditors. The process of issuing carbon credits requires an audit for each issuance, which is termed a verification audit under all three carbon standards.

The magnitude of all fees aggregated is significant, particularly for South African project developers who contend with the added challenge of dollar exchange rates. Indeed, it is common practise for projects to issue carbon credits in intervals, such as every 2 or 5 years, to enhance financial viability and lead to favourable revenue outcomes. But the

challenges go beyond the total costs involved in the project cycle and issuance of credits that should factored in the calculations; they also involve issues of capacity and knowledge. The world of carbon markets is complex and there is usually a division of labour to undertake preliminary steps such as the pre-feasibility studies due a lack of understanding of the opportunities and conditions to register a project. Therefore, one should also include the process of recruiting consultancy firms and brokers who would trade credits eventually. In practice, it is also common that such carbon projects are funded by external investors with ownership of the credits after issuance. Consequently, calculations change as the revenues associated with the carbon project would then be limited to the financial support provided by such funders, which is necessary lower than the proceeds from the sales of credits.

CONCLUSIONS

We studied the possibility that value chains processing biomass from invasive alien trees in South Africa could become financially sustainable owing to incentives provided by carbon

FIGURE 7 General project development cycle for carbon credit projects

pricing mechanisms. We conclude that such a possibility exists and should be considered seriously in other geographies considering the increasing costs associated with invasive species worldwide.

The eligibility is highly dependent on the standards and their criteria that rest mostly on two different concepts: waste biomass and renewable biomass. While the latter opens the door widely to eligibility, the former one is subject to interpretation. In a context of increasing awareness about tree invasions, which is exemplified by specific standard rules that apply to invasive alien plants, we conclude that interpretations will increasingly lean towards eligibility.

Our calculations show that carbon incentives represent up to 20% of the final product value with a rather optimistic price for carbon credits at US\$ 15/t CO₂-eq. In the case of biochar, incentives could be anywhere between 4–40% of the product value due to its specific status as Carbon Dioxide Removal and co-benefits.

When translated in the increase in maximum affordable supply costs of biomass, our findings show that carbon incentives could significantly expand the scope of accessible sources of biomass with an increase between 8–95% at US\$ 15/tCO₂-eq. In the case of biochar specifically, high-value credits would secure profits even with biochar prices below the current market prices. This holds potential to change investors' decisions.

Our analysis led to reflections on the articulation with adaptation-based funding. In an ideal world, land clearing to eradicate invasive trees should be funded for adaptation purposes, including through the Green Climate Fund and other international sustainable financing initiatives. This would provide the means to supply biomass at scale and sustain both an energy transition and the large-scale production of biochar while leading to an eligibility of associated value chains to issue carbon credits. Such an eligibility would in turn provide more financial support to these businesses and a bioeconomy virtuous cycle would be kickstarted.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We would like to thank the two anonymous reviewers who dedicated time to the formulation of constructive comments that helped us improve the article. We are also grateful to the editor for his reactivity and efficient handling of the manuscript towards publication. This work was funded in part by MarginUp! (Project 101082089 with the European Research Executive Agency). The French Ministry for Europe and Foreign Affairs supported the first author. However, the views and opinions expressed are those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, the European Commission or the French Ministry for Europe and Foreign Affairs. Neither the European Union, the granting authority nor the French Ministry for Europe and Foreign Affairs can be held responsible for them.

REFERENCES

- AFRANE, S., AMPAH, J.D., YUSUF, A.A., JINJUAN, Z., YANG, P., CHEN, J.L., and MAO, G. 2024. Role of negative emission technologies in South Africa's pathway to net zero emissions by 2050. *Energy for Sustainable Development* **79**: 101401.
- AKINBAMI, O.M., OKE, S.R., and BODUNRIN, M.O. 2021. The state of renewable energy development in South Africa: An overview. *Alexandria Engineering Journal* **60**: 5077–5093. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2021.03.065>
- BIOCHAR WORKS, DELANEY FORESTRY SERVICES, FORLIANCE and SOUTH POLE. 2022. Methodology for Biochar utilization in soil and non-soil applications (VM004). Verified Carbon Standard.
- BUNGE EMISSIONS HOLDINGS SARL. 2012. Validation report: Grahamstown Invasive Biomass Power Project. Report No. CDM.12.VAL.034 (version 3).
- CDM EXECUTIVE BOARD. 2012. Project Design Document (PDD): Grahamstown Invasive Biomass Power Project (version 3). United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change. https://cdm.unfccc.int/Projects/DB/KBS_Cert1353665832.64/view
- CLEAN DEVELOPMENT MECHANISM. 2022a. AMS-III Small Scale Methodology: Biogas / Biomass Thermal Applications for Households / Small Users - Version 06.0. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change.
- CLEAN DEVELOPMENT MECHANISM. 2022b. AM0036 Large Scale Methodology: Use of Biomass in Heat Generation Equipment - Version 07.0. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change.
- EVERSON, C.S., CLULOW, A.D., BECKER, M., WATSON, A., NGUBO, C., BULCOCK, H., MENGISTU, M., LORENTZ, S., and DEMLIE, M. 2014. The long term impact of *Acacia mearnsii* trees on evaporation, streamflow, low flows and ground water resources. Phase II: Understanding the controlling environmental variables and soil water processes over a full crop rotation.
- FOREST TRENDS' ECOSYSTEM MARKETPLACE. 2023. State of the Voluntary Carbon Markets 2023. Forest Trends Association. Washington D.C.
- FORSYTH, G.G., LE MAITRE, D.C., O'FARRELL, P.J., and VAN WILGEN, B.W. 2012. The prioritisation of invasive alien plant control projects using a multi-criteria decision model informed by stakeholder input and spatial data. *Journal of Environmental Management* **103**: 51–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2012.01.034>
- HOLDEN, P., REBELO, A.J., WOLSKI, P., ODOULAMI, R.C., LAWAL, K.A., KIMUTAI, J., NKEMELANG, T., and NEW, M.G. 2021. Nature-based Solutions in Mountain catchments reduce impact of anthropogenic climate change on hydrological drought streamflow. *Communications Earth and Environment* **3**: 51. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-022-00379-9>
- HOLMES, P.M., ESLER, K.J., VAN WILGEN, B.W., and RICHARDSON, D.M. 2020. Ecological restoration of ecosystems degraded by invasive alien plants in South African Fynbos: Is spontaneous succession a viable strategy? *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0035919X.2020.1781291>

- HUGO, W. (Ed). 2016. BioEnergy Atlas for South Africa – Synopsi Report. Department of Science and Technology. Pretoria. South Africa. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15493/SAEON.BEA.DOCS.10000001>
- IPBES. 2023. Thematic Assessment Report on Invasive Alien Species and their Control of the Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. ROY, H.E., PAUCHARD, A., STOETT, P., and RENARD TRUONG, T. (eds.). IPBES secretariat. Bonn. Germany. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7430682>
- KONZ, J., COHEN, B., and VAN DER MERWE, A. 2015. Assessment of the potential to produce biochar and its application to South African soils as a mitigation measure. Department of Environmental Affairs. Pretoria. South Africa.
- KOTZE, J.D.F., BEUKES, H., VAN DEN BERG, E., and NEWBY, T. 2010. National Invasive Alien Plant Survey. Agricultural Research Council. Institute for Soil, Climate and Water. GW/A/2010/21.
- LE MAITRE, D.C., VAN WILGEN, B.W., GELDERBLUM, C.M., BAILEY, C., CHAPMAN, R.A., and NEL, J.A. 2002. Invasive alien trees and water resources in South Africa: case studies of the costs and benefits of management. *Forest Ecology and Management* **160**: 143–159. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127\(01\)00474-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127(01)00474-1)
- LE MAITRE, D.C., FORSYTH, G.G., DZIKITI, S., and GUSH, M.B. 2016. Estimates of the impacts of invasive alien plants on water flows in South Africa. *Water SA* **42**: 659–672.
- LEFEBVRE, D., FAWZY, S., AQUIJE, C.A., OSMAN, A.I., DRAPER, K.A., and TRABOLD, T.A. 2023. Biomass residue to carbon dioxide removal: quantifying the global impact of biochar. *Biochar* **5**: 65.
- MBOPHA, M.S., MARAIS, C., KLEYNHANS, T.E., and ESLER, K.J. 2021. Unlocking and securing ecological infrastructure investments: The needs and willingness to invest and institutional support mechanisms used. *S Afr J Sci.* **117**(9/10).
- NDHLOVU, T., MILTON-DEAN, S.J., and ESLER, K.J. 2011. Impact of *Prosopis* (mesquite) invasion and clearing on the grazing capacity of semiarid Nama Karoo rangeland, South Africa. *Afr. J. Range Forage Sci.* **28**: 129–137. <https://doi.org/10.2989/10220119.2011.642095>
- NERSA. 2011 (March). Review of Renewable Energy Feed-In Tariffs, NERSA Consultation Paper, National Energy Regulator of South Africa.
- NUNEZ, M.A., DAVIS, K.T., DIMARCO, R.D., PELTZER, D.A., PARITSIS, J., MAXWELL, B.D., and PAUCHARD, A. 2021. Should tree invasions be used in treeless ecosystems to mitigate climate change? *Front Ecol Environ* **19**(6): 334–341. doi:10.1002/fee.2346
- O'CONNOR, T.G., and VAN WILGEN, B.W. 2020. "Chapter 16: The impact of invasive alien plants on rangelands in South Africa", pp. 459–87, In B.W. van Wilgen et al. (eds), Biological invasions in South Africa, Invading Nature. *Springer Series in Invasion Ecology* **14**. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-32394-3_16
- PETERSEN, A.M., OKORO, O., PREEZ, J.D., and GORGENS, J.F. 2020. Evaluation of Biorefining Scenarios for Advanced Fuels production from Triticale Grain. *Energy & Fuels* **34**: 11003–13. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.energyfuels.0c01568>.
- PIRARD, R. 2023. Rethinking the role of value-added industries for invasive trees in South Africa. *International Forestry Review* **25**(2). <https://doi.org/10.1505/146554823837244428>
- PIRARD, R. 2025. Is biochar a Carbon Dioxide Removal? Bois et Forêts des Tropiques. Forthcoming.
- PURO.EARTH. 2022. Puro Standard Biochar Methodology: Edition 2022 V2. Puro.earth.
- SBP. 2023. SBP Standard 1: Feedstock Compliance (version 2.0). Sustainable Biomass Program.
- SCHMIDT, H.P., and WILSON, K. 2014. The 55 uses of biochar. The Biochar Journal. Arbaz. Switzerland. ISSN 2297-1114 www.biochar-journal.org/en/ct/2 Version of 12 th May 2014 Accessed: 13.09.2024
- SHUKLA, P.R., SKEA, J., SLADE, R., AL KHOURDAJIE, A., VAN DIEMEN, R., MCCOLLUM, D., PATHAK, M., SOME, S., VYAS, P., FRADERA, R., BELKACEMI, M., HASIJA, A., LISBOA, G., LUZ, S., MALLEY, J. (Eds.). 2022. *Climate Change 2022: Mitigation of Climate Change. Contribution of Working Group III to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, doi:10.1017/9781009157926.001
- SPINELLI, R., and MAGAGNOTTI, N. 2014. Determining long-term chipper usage, productivity and fuel consumption. *Biomass and Bioenergy* **66**: 442–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2014.04.016>
- STAFFORD, W.H.L., VON MALTITZ, G.P., and WATSON, H.K. 2018. Reducing the costs of landscape restoration by using invasive alien plant biomass for bioenergy. *WIREs Energy Environ* **7**: e272. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wene.272>
- THE WORLD BANK. 2022. State and Trends of Carbon Pricing 2022 (May). World Bank. Washington DC. Doi: 10.1596/978-1-4648-1895-0.
- TOMA-NOW. 2021. Business model for biochar, activated carbon and wood vinegar ("BAW") produced from cleared alien invasive plants in the Karatara river catchment. Western Cape Government DEA DP. Cape Town. South Africa.
- TROUWLOON, D., STRECK, C., CHAGAS, T., and MARTINUS, G. 2023. Understanding the use of carbon credits by companies: A review of the defining elements of corporate climate claims. *Global Challenges* **7**. <https://doi.org/10.1002/gch2.202200158>
- VAN WILGEN, B.W., and WANNENBURGH, A. 2016. Co-facilitating invasive species control, water conservation and poverty relief: achievements and challenges in South Africa's Working for water programme. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain* **19**: 7–17. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2015.08.012>.
- VAN WILGEN, B.W., WANNENBURGH, A., and WILSON, J.R.U. 2022. A review of two decades of government support for managing alien plant invasions in South Africa. *Biological Conservation* **274**. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109741>